

THE DYNAMIC ENVIRONMENT SIMULATOR AS A ROBOTIC SYSTEM: KINEMATIC ISSUES

Rodney G. Roberts

Daniel W. Repperger

* Armstrong Laboratory
AL/CFBS BLDG 29
2245 Third Street

Wright Patterson AFB OH 45433-7008

Abstract—This paper examines the problem of simulating angular velocity fields that may, for example, be experienced by a pilot during a supermaneuverable flight trajectory. The ability to simulate angular velocity fields has important applications in the study of certain physiological effects encountered by pilots during these unusual flight scenarios. The simulations are to be performed using a centrifuge simulator called the Dynamic Environment Simulator (DES) located in the Armstrong Laboratory of Wright-Patterson Air Force Base. Some of the kinematic issues relating to the motion control of the DES are examined in the paper.

I. INTRODUCTION

With the recent advances in the control of high performance aircraft, the study of the physiological aspects of flight is becoming increasingly more important. The physiological stresses encountered by a pilot during a high acceleration maneuver can be an important factor in determining whether the maneuver can be performed safely. A trained pilot properly equipped with a G protection suit can withstand turns of up to nine G's (nine times the force of gravity); however, high thrust-to-weight fighters are capable of sustained high load factor maneuvers which exceed pilot G tolerance, resulting in gravity induced loss of consciousness (GLOC). Spatial disorientation during flight is also a hazardous problem which can have fatal consequences. Due to these physiological limitations on the pilot, advanced fighters cannot always realize their performance capabilities.

The motion fields experienced by a pilot can, to some degree, be approximated using a centrifuge simulator. Such devices are thus instrumental in studying G stress and pilot disorientation as well as for studies in safety and training pilots in a controlled environment. This is particularly true when studying flight scenarios involving

supermaneuverable flight since many of the proposed supermaneuvers have not actually been flown [3]. This paper will examine the problem of simulating angular velocity fields using a centrifuge as a motion simulator. The device considered here is called the Dynamic Environment Simulator (DES). The DES is man-rated three-axis centrifuge located in the Armstrong Laboratory of Wright-Patterson Air Force Base in Dayton, Ohio. Many of the motion control techniques typically applied to robotics are also applicable to the DES. These techniques can be used for controlling the endpoint of the centrifuge where the test subject is located as well as for analyzing the centrifuge's ability to emulate angular velocities a pilot would experience during certain flight maneuvers.

The paper is outlined in the following manner: Section II will describe the DES and discuss its kinematics relative to its end effector orientation. Section III is concerned with different manipulability and dexterity measures for the centrifuge. These measures can be evaluated using the singular value decomposition (SVD) of the Jacobian associated with the rotations of the centrifuge. The SVD is further used in Section IV to determine which angular velocities are readily achievable at or near a singular configuration. Section V discusses some of the kinematic limitations of the centrifuge and how constraints on the joint velocities limit the set of angular velocities which can be simulated on the centrifuge. Finally, conclusions appear in Section VI.

II. THE CENTRIFUGE

The Dynamic Environment Simulator (DES), shown in Fig. 1, is a three-axis centrifuge consisting of a 19 foot main arm weighing 180 tons, a fork, and a cab. Built in the mid 1960's and man-rated in 1969, it is the only three degree of freedom centrifuge used for this multiaxis research within the United States Air Force. The cab contains an adjustable seat for test subjects and a display screen. The seat parameters θ_t and θ_y , which are defined in Fig. 2, represent the pitch and yaw orientation of the

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seat. These parameters are adjustable prior to a run, but are fixed during the centrifuge's motion. One of the issues that will be examined in this work is the question of how to take advantage of the freedom to choose θ_t and θ_y a priori. The configuration of the DES is denoted by the vector $\theta = [\theta_1 \ \theta_2 \ \theta_3]^T$ where θ_1 represents the clockwise rotation of the main arm when viewed from above, θ_2 represents the fork rotation, and θ_3 represents the cab rotation.

The kinematics for the manipulator with respect to rotations is given in [4] in the form

$$\Omega = J\dot{\theta} \quad (1)$$

where Ω is the angular velocity at the centrifuge's seat and is configured about a body axis coordinate system located within the pilot, $\dot{\theta}$ is the time derivative of θ , and J is the manipulator Jacobian for rotations

$$J = \begin{bmatrix} c_t s_y & -c_t s_t + s_t c_t c_y & s_1 c_2 s_t + c_1 c_2 c_t c_y + s_2 c_t s_y \\ -c_y & s_1 s_y & c_1 c_2 s_y - s_2 c_y \\ -s_t s_y & -c_1 c_t - s_1 s_t c_y & s_1 c_2 c_t - c_1 c_2 s_t c_y - s_2 s_t s_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $c_i = \cos \theta_i$ and $s_i = \sin \theta_i$.

The manipulator is controlled using resolved motion rate control. The required joint velocities $\dot{\theta}$ for a given angular motion field are found by inverting (1). Thus the motion field is found by using the relation

$$\dot{\theta} = J^{-1}\Omega. \quad (3)$$

Unfortunately, certain configurations of the centrifuge result in a singular Jacobian. At such configurations, the dimension of the column space of J is no longer three so that not all angular velocities can be obtained. Near the singularities, (3) can result in prohibitively high joint velocities which may not be achievable by the centrifuge due to finite torque constraints as well as other dynamic limitations.

III. PERFORMANCE MEASURES FOR THE CENTRIFUGE

In order to quantify the performance of the manipulator at a given configuration, robotists often use a variety of manipulability and dexterity measures [1]. These measures can be used to determine optimal operating configurations and to identify configurations where using (3) may result in difficulties. A very commonly applied measure is the manipulability index [6], which is given by

$$w = \sqrt{\det(JJ^T)}. \quad (4)$$

Note that this quantity is zero precisely when J is singular. Another commonly used measure is the minimum

singular value of J . This provides a good measure of the nearness to a singularity in the sense that it is the distance of J to the nearest singular matrix in the matrix 2-norm sense. Another possible measure is the condition number of J , which is defined as

$$c(J) = \|J\| \|J^{-1}\|. \quad (5)$$

It is well known that for this definition, the condition number of a matrix is given by the ratio of the largest singular value to the smallest singular value. An ideally conditioned matrix has the condition number one while an ill-conditioned matrix has a "large" condition number.

All three of the manipulability measures described above are functions of the singular values of J , with the manipulability index of J being given as the product of its singular values. Thus, a knowledge of the singular value decomposition (SVD) provides all the necessary information for these measures. As will be seen in the next section, the SVD also provides information on how the control based on (3) behaves at or near the singularities of the centrifuge.

In general, the SVD of a matrix is difficult to calculate analytically. Fortunately, the SVD of J in equation (2) can be written analytically. The Jacobian J can be decomposed as the product of two matrices, one as a function of the fixed parameters θ_t and θ_y and the other as a function of the dynamic parameters θ_1 and θ_2 , i.e.,

$$J = T(\theta_t, \theta_y)\bar{J}(\theta_1, \theta_2) \quad (6)$$

where T is an orthogonal matrix which can be factored as

$$T(\theta_t, \theta_y) = \begin{bmatrix} c\theta_t & 0 & s\theta_t \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -s\theta_t & 0 & c\theta_t \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} s\theta_y & c\theta_y & 0 \\ -c\theta_y & s\theta_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

and \bar{J} is given by

$$\bar{J} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & s\theta_2 \\ 0 & s\theta_1 & c\theta_1 c\theta_2 \\ 0 & -c\theta_1 & s\theta_1 c\theta_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

Now \bar{J} can be further decomposed into

$$\bar{J} = M_1(\theta_1)M_2(\theta_2) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & s\theta_1 & c\theta_1 \\ 0 & -c\theta_1 & s\theta_1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & s\theta_2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c\theta_2 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

Let $R_x(\phi)$, $R_y(\phi)$, and $R_z(\phi)$ denote the rotation matrices corresponding to a rotation of ϕ radians about the x , y , and z axes, respectively. The matrix J can then be written as

$$J = R_y(-\theta_t)R_z(\theta_y - \frac{\pi}{2})R_x(\theta_1 - \frac{\pi}{2})M_2(\theta_2). \quad (10)$$

The matrix M_2 is a relatively simple function of the single parameter θ_2 . Its singular value decomposition can be calculated analytically and is given by

$$M_2 = U_2 \Sigma V^T \quad (11)$$

where

$$U_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1+s\theta_2)} & 0 & -\sqrt{\frac{1}{2}(1-s\theta_2)} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{c\theta_2}{\sqrt{2(1+s\theta_2)}} & 0 & \frac{c\theta_2}{\sqrt{2(1-s\theta_2)}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (12)$$

$$\Sigma = \text{diag}(\sqrt{1+s\theta_2}, 1, \sqrt{1-s\theta_2}), \quad (13)$$

and

$$V = R_y\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & 0 & \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (14)$$

Combining (10) and (11) yields the SVD of J , which is given by

$$J = U \Sigma V^T \quad (15)$$

where

$$U = R_y(-\theta_1) R_z(\theta_y - \frac{\pi}{2}) R_x(\theta_1 - \frac{\pi}{2}) U_2 \quad (16)$$

Note that the singular values in (13) are not necessarily written in ascending order as is typically done for the SVD. The maximum and minimum singular values will alternate between $\sqrt{1+s\theta_2}$ and $\sqrt{1-s\theta_2}$, depending on the sign of $\sin \theta_2$.

The performance measures can now be given:

$$w = |c\theta_2| \quad (17)$$

$$\sigma_{\min}(J) = \sqrt{1-|s\theta_2|} \quad (18)$$

$$\text{cond}(J) = \sqrt{\frac{1+|s\theta_2|}{1-|s\theta_2|}}. \quad (19)$$

It is clear that the optimal configurations occur precisely when $\sin \theta_2 = 0$ while the worse possible configurations occur when $\cos \theta_2 = 0$. Note that the fixed parameters θ_1 and θ_y do not influence the performance measures described. These performance measures however are relative to all possible trajectories; for a given motion field, one can still adjust the parameters θ_1 and θ_y to obtain a better simulation.

IV. THE CENTRIFUGE'S BEHAVIOR AT A SINGULARITY

The SVD of J also provides tools for analyzing the centrifuge's behavior at or near a singular configuration. While singular configurations are usually avoided in most

robotic applications due to the lack of full motion control at such a configuration, there are often advantages associated with singular configurations, as will be seen in the next section. A variety of numerical techniques such as damped least squares can be used to control the manipulator as it passes through or close to a singularity [2], [5]. Singular configurations are characterized by the determinant of J being zero. Since the determinant of J is $c\theta_2$, the singular configurations of the centrifuge are given by

$$\theta_2 = \frac{\pi}{2} + n\pi \quad n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots \quad (20)$$

The inverse of J is

$$J^{-1} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \frac{1}{\sigma_i} \mathbf{v}_i \mathbf{u}_i^T \quad (21)$$

where \mathbf{u}_i and \mathbf{v}_i are the i -th columns of U and V , respectively. This representation of J^{-1} provides additional information concerning how the joints move. In particular, from (14) and (21), it follows that the joint velocity $\dot{\theta}_2$ required of the second joint is decoupled from the velocities required of the first and third joints and is given by

$$\dot{\theta}_2 = \mathbf{u}_2^T \Omega. \quad (22)$$

Since \mathbf{u}_2 is a unit vector, it follows from the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality that

$$|\dot{\theta}_2| \leq \|\Omega\|, \quad (23)$$

which implies that the magnitude of the joint velocity $\dot{\theta}_2$ is bounded at each time t by $\|\Omega(t)\|$. This is not true for the first and third joints since arbitrarily high joint velocities may result from using (3). It follows from (13), (14), and (21) that when excessive joint velocities are required due to nearness to a singularity, the first and third joint velocities will be roughly equal in magnitude, with a sign difference in the case when $s\theta_2 = 1$.

It is also possible to characterize obtainable and unobtainable angular velocities at a singularity as well as the angular velocities which result in excessive joint velocities near the singularity. The angular velocities which are readily obtainable are in

$$\mathcal{V}_s = \text{span} \left\{ T \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, T \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ s\theta_1 \\ -c\theta_1 \end{bmatrix} \right\} \quad (24)$$

where T is given in (7). The angular velocities which are not so readily obtainable near singularities have a component in

$$\mathcal{V}_u = \text{span} \left\{ T \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ c\theta_1 \\ s\theta_1 \end{bmatrix} \right\}. \quad (25)$$

At a singularity, (24) determines the space of angular velocities which can be simulated.

V. KINEMATIC LIMITATIONS OF THE CENTRIFUGE

Since the centrifuge is a physical device, there are inherent limitations on its ability to emulate angular velocity fields. This section examines performance limitations of the centrifuge based on its kinematic limitations. In particular, the envelope of angular velocities which are obtainable by the centrifuge will be derived using the factorization of J given by equations (6) through (9). In order to accomplish this goal, the Jacobian equation will be written as

$$\tilde{\Omega} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & s\theta_2 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c\theta_2 \end{bmatrix} \dot{\theta} \quad (26)$$

where

$$\tilde{\Omega} = R_x(-\theta_1 + \frac{\pi}{2})R_z(-\theta_y + \frac{\pi}{2})R_y(\theta_t)\Omega. \quad (27)$$

The important point to note is that $\tilde{\Omega}$ can be made into any rotation of Ω by properly choosing θ_1 and the seat parameters θ_t and θ_y . Thus, in terms of maximizing the envelope of possible angular velocities, it is sufficient to only consider the problem of maximizing $\|\tilde{\Omega}\|$ subject to the kinematic constraints on $\dot{\theta}$. For the case where the kinematic constraint has the form $\|\dot{\theta}\| \leq B$, the largest singular value is at a maximum when $\|\tilde{\Omega}\|$ is maximized. Thus the maximum $\|\tilde{\Omega}\|$ is $\sqrt{2}B$. Note that at such a configuration, J is singular. Since the joint actuators are independent, it is more realistic to have joint velocity limits of the form $|\dot{\theta}_i| \leq B_i$. In order to maximize the angular velocities in this case, $\|\tilde{\Omega}\|$ is expanded

$$\|\tilde{\Omega}\|^2 = \|\dot{\theta}\|^2 + 2 \sin \theta_2 \dot{\theta}_1 \dot{\theta}_3. \quad (28)$$

Clearly, $|\sin \theta_2| = 1$ at the maximum so that

$$\max \|\tilde{\Omega}\|^2 = B_1^2 + B_2^2 + B_3^2 + 2B_1B_3. \quad (29)$$

Note that once again, the centrifuge is at a singular configuration when a maximum occurs. The joint velocity limits of the DES are currently $|\dot{\theta}_1| \leq 5.86$ rad/sec, $|\dot{\theta}_2| \leq 3.14$ rad/sec, and $|\dot{\theta}_3| \leq 3.14$ rad/sec so that angular velocities of magnitudes up to 9.53 rad/sec can be simulated, well within the requirements of a supermaneuver.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has examined some of the kinematic issues related to the motion control of a centrifuge simulator called the Dynamic Environment Simulator (DES). The centrifuge's manipulability was quantified using some

of the measures commonly found in the current robotics literature. The kinematic singularities of the centrifuge were also identified, and the obtainable angular motion fields passing through a singularity were characterized. Finally, the set of angular velocities which can be achieved was derived given the kinematic limitations of the centrifuge.

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The Three Axes Simulator

Fig. 1 The DES (Dynamic Environment Simulator).

Fig. 2 The Body Axis Coordinate System.